

CoRDI

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A Database and Repository for Catalysis Data in NOMAD

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Abstract

In the era of big data and open science, effective research data management (RDM) is essential for scientific progress and collaboration.[1] However, experimental catalysis research lags behind other disciplines, due to the prevalence of custom-built equipment dominating in the laboratories, individualized research questions and procedures, and complex data structures. The lack of community-wide standards hinders the comparison of catalysis data generated in different laboratories and the application of machine learning models that require large datasets.[2] Here, we present a RDM solution developed in FAIRmat within the context of experimental catalysis research, emphasizing the role of structured data and open repositories in enhancing data sharing, reuse, and reproducibility.

The RDM solution is based on the software NOMAD, a versatile platform for managing materials research data.[3] We have developed a plugin that enables NOMAD to handle catalysis data. This plugin provides two main functionalities: i) schemas to structure and upload catalysis data and domain-specific metadata, and ii) an app to visualize, summarize, and browse existing entries.

For each entry, an underlying schema needs to be selected, and data and metadata can be filled either manually directly in the graphical user interface (GUI) or, preferably for larger datasets, by uploading pre-structured tables in CSV or XLSX format or directly in JSON files. Using these schemas ensures that the data is consistently formatted and can be easily analyzed with the tools available in NOMAD. By linking the terms in the schema with definitions in the community-developed vocabulary Voc4Cat,[4] an initiative by NFDI4Cat, we aim to enhance interoperability and facilitate data exchange across different research groups.

The NOMAD catalysis app is designed to visualize and interact with uploaded catalysis data. This tool acts as a search filter, and visualization interface in one. Users can filter data by various parameters, including catalysts, reactions, and reaction conditions. One of the most

powerful features of the app are the interactive scatterplots that display critical catalyst properties such as conversion and selectivity. Users can customize these plots, with the ability to directly inspecting the original data entry just by clicking on a data point.

The NOMAD catalysis plugin is designed to be user-friendly, ensuring that researchers can easily upload, manage, and analyze their data and addresses a critical need for standardized data structures and open repositories. By providing a comprehensive and intuitive platform, we aim to lower the barriers to data sharing and collaboration, ultimately accelerating scientific discovery in catalysis.

Keywords: RDM, Database, Repository, NOMAD, Catalysis

Resources

- nomad-catalysis-plugin. <https://github.com/FAIRmat-NFDI/nomad-catalysis-plugin> "A plugin that enables NOMAD to handle catalysis data."
- nomad-lab. <https://nomad-lab.eu/nomad-lab/>, <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.05388> "a browser-based software solution for research data management in material sciences"

Author contributions

J. Schumann – data curation, software development (plugin), validation, visualization, writing – original draft

M. Götte – software (initial code contribution), discussion about data structures, data curation

H. Nässtrom – software (code review and contributions)

L. Himanen – software development

A. Moshantaf – data curation

M. Scheidgen – resources provision, software development

J.A. Marquez – conceptualization, supervision, project administration

A. Trunschke – conceptualization, funding acquisition, supervision, writing – review & editing

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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